

Municipal Solid Waste: A Strategic Resource

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ABSTRACT

A largely rural country, with only 18% of the population living in urban areas, Nepal is urbanizing rapidly with urban population growth rates of up to 7%. With a population growth rate of about 4% per year, the municipalities of Kathmandu Valley are facing the unprecedented challenges of rapid urbanization and modernization on a metropolitan scale. The average rate of municipal solid waste (MSW) generation is 341.63 gm per capita per day in five municipalities (Kathmandu, Lalitpur, Bhaktapur, Thimi and Kirtipur) of Kathmandu Valley. The increasing and unmanageable waste volume is a major concern for all the municipalities. In Kathmandu Valley most of the MSW is land-filled, leading to a significant pressure on the environment. The truth is very little is recycled. In this paper, the basic indicators of MSW are analyzed: generation per capita per day, total waste generation, and waste generation from household, commercial and institutional activities etc. The municipalities of Kathmandu valley are focusing on sweeping the street, collecting and transferring the waste to the landfill rather than minimizing the waste. The important priorities to consider MSW as a strategic resource are: reduction of waste at source, re-use, compost, recycle and recovery which will minimize the disposal volume and increase the life of landfill.

KEY WORDS: Municipal Solid Waste (MSW), waste generation, resource, recycling

1. INTRODUCTION

Everyday humans generate waste, and it is an unavoidable by-product of human activities. As the world moves ahead, the amount of municipal solid waste is outpacing the rate of urbanization. Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) is all types of solid waste generated by households, institutions and commercial establishments and collected usually by local government bodies [2]. Solid Waste Management is the systematic control of generation, prevention, characterization, monitoring, treatment, recovery, reuse and residual disposition of solid waste [2]. There are various types of solid waste including municipal (residential, institutional, commercial), agricultural and special (healthcare, household hazardous waste, sewage sludge). The term usually relates to materials produced by human activity and the process is generally undertaken to reduce their effect on health, environment or aesthetics.

World Bank estimates that roughly 3 billion urban residents generated an average 1.2 billion kg per capita per day (1.3 billion tonnes per year) in the year 2012. By 2025, this is expected to increase to 4.3 billion urban residents generating about 1.42 kg per capita per day of MSW (2.2 billion tonnes per year). This represents a 900 million tonnes increase in a little over a decade, a near doubling of the total volume of MSW generated globally today [3].

The rate of generation of municipal solid waste in the developing countries is increasing with an increase of population, technological development, and the changes in the life styles of the people which is posing a great environmental and public health problem. The solid waste generation in cities of Asian developing countries is 0.2 to 1.7 kg per capita per day. In Nepal the rate of solid waste generation is 317 gram per capita per day whereas in Kathmandu Valley it ranges from 252.9 gm/capita/day to 464.61 gm/capita/day in 2013/14 [6].

Asia is home to 66 of the 100 fastest-growing urban areas (half of these in China). Half of the world's urban population lives in Asia. According to Central Bureau of Statistics, Nepal, the population of Nepal has reached 27.95 million in April 2015 which was 26.49 million in the year 2011 [6]. A largely rural country, with only 18% of the population living in urban areas, Nepal is urbanizing rapidly with urban population growth rates of up to 7%. With a population of 2.5 million people already, the Kathmandu Valley is growing at 4% per year, one the fastest growing metropolitan areas in South Asia, and the first region in Nepal to face the unprecedented challenges of rapid urbanization and modernization on a metropolitan scale. The sustainability of urbanization in Kathmandu Valley is threatened by a lack of effective planning and large and growing infrastructure deficits [3].

The Nepal government is spending substantial amounts of budget just to sustain the treatment and management of municipal solid waste in Kathmandu valley. Waste handling practice in municipalities of Kathmandu valley is labor intensive, and disposal system does not meet environmental standard. Mixture of organic to inorganic and hazardous to non-hazardous wastes is the composition of municipal waste of Kathmandu.

Nowadays waste is not considered as a waste but it is one of the most significant and valuable resources available in our society continuously. It can even become a source of income and of strategic resources for making new products. To manage waste so that it does not harm people or the environment, there is a need to reduce the amount of the waste generated and turn it back into useful materials and resources. Everyone, but especially industries, institutions, commercial organizations and government offices, must take responsibility for the wastes they generate and for preventing waste in the first place by making and using products that are reusable, recyclable, or compostable. The objective of this study is to assess the

generation of municipal solid waste (MSW) and to propose the emerging opportunities for MSW as a strategic resource for reducing and managing the waste in the Kathmandu valley.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sources and Methodology

In preparing this paper, primary and secondary research sources have been reviewed. The primary data and information have been obtained from phone and in person interviews with the authorities of Solid Waste Management and Resource Mobilization Centre (SWM&RMC), Kathmandu. This paper also includes secondary data source from report, journals, and posts on the websites. The reference period for data analysis used is from 2008 to 2014. These primary and secondary research sources have been utilized for qualitative and quantitative analysis.

The research design used is descriptive research to explain different factors related to solid waste generation and its management. Out of 191 municipalities declared in Nepal in 2014, five sample municipalities – Bhaktapur, Kathmandu, Kirtipur, Lalitpur and MadhyapurThimi of Kathmandu valley have been chosen for the study on the basis of convenience.

There are many types of wastes generated in Nepal including household, commercial, industrial, construction and demolition, agricultural, sewage, mining and quarrying. Of the various types of waste generated, municipal solid waste (MSW) represents the data relevant to this paper. MSW is primarily composed of waste that is produced by the household, but also includes some commercial and industrial waste similar in nature to household waste and would otherwise be deposited in municipal landfill sites.

2.2 Municipalities under Study

The total areas covered by municipalities in Kathmandu valley are 49.45 square kilometre, 15.15 sq. km., 14.76 sq. km, 11.11 sq km and 6.56 sq. km by Kathmandu, Lalitpur, Kirtipur, MadhyapurThimi and Bhaktapur respectively.

Kathmandu has the highest population of 10,03,285, followed by Lalitpur (2,26,728), Thimi (84,142), Bhaktapur (83,658) and Kirtipur has the lowest population of 67,171.

Figure 2.1 Total Area and Total Population of Municipalities in 2011

2.3 Trend of Municipal Solid Waste Generation

The average per capita solid waste generation is 317gm/capita/day in Nepal. Figure 2.2 shows that there is increasing trend of solid waste generation (mt/day) in five municipalities of Kathmandu valley.

Figure 2.2 Solid Waste Generation (mt/day) by Municipalities of Kathmandu Valley

Among the five municipalities, Kathmandu has very high rate of solid waste generation ranging from 29.9 tons per day in the year 2006/07, which drastically increased to 466.14 tons of solid waste per day in the fiscal year 2013/14. In 2015 the solid waste generation started increasing at a significant rate. After Kathmandu, the other solid waste generators are Lalitpur, Bhaktapur, Thimi and Kirtipur

municipalities which generated 84.3, 28.9, 23.01, and 16.99 metric tons of solid waste per day respectively in fiscal year 2013/14.

One of the major reasons for this increase in waste generation rate is floating and migrating population from different parts of Nepal to the Kathmandu valley, particularly after People's War. Not only this but also the change in living standard including food habits of the people who started opting for fast foods, increased use of materials like paper, plastics, cans etc. is the other significant factor. On the basis of area covered and population density, other municipalities have a moderate type of growth in waste generation.

2.4 Types of Wastes in Municipalities

In Kathmandu Metropolitan City (MPC) the household waste, commercial waste, and institutional waste are generated highly i.e. 233.07, 203.49 and 29.58 tons per day in the year 2013. The second largest waste generator is Lalitpur Municipality comprising of 42.15, 36.8 and 5.35 tons per day of household waste, commercial waste, and institutional waste respectively.

Kathmandu MPC alone produced 233.07 tons of household waste per day in the year 2013 that is very high compared to other municipalities that produce about 10.19 to 42.15 tons/day. The main reason for this is high population density of 20,289 person per square kilometre and migrating population as it is the heart of Nepal. The other reason is the average household size which is about 4 to 5 generating 151.43 to 232.31 gm per capita per day of waste in the municipalities under study.

Figure 2.3 Types of Wastes in Municipalities of Kathmandu Valley

2.5 URBANIZATION IN MUNICIPALITIES

Urbanization has brought shift in the life style of people in the Kathmandu Valley. Kathmandu is fast becoming a shopping paradise with new malls opening up every now and then with an assortment of products ranging from branded cloth wears to household items.

Not only this the opening of the pubs and clubs, disco and night clubs, cinema, casino, fast food industries and restaurants, etc. have increased the municipality solid waste in Kathmandu valley. Unplanned urban development in the Kathmandu valley has led to rapid and uncontrolled extension; irregular, substandard, and inaccessible housing development.

Kathmandu Metropolitan City (MPC) is the highest household, commercial and institutional waste generator among the five municipalities under study. The reason for this is number of industries and institutions registered in Kathmandu valley. The data available in November 2014 from Ministry of Industries of Nepal shows that total 3415 companies or industries are registered in the Kathmandu valley. Out of this, 78.24% industries belongs to Kathmandu district only including 1046 companies of service sector, 930 industries of manufacturing, 572 related to tourism and rest 124 related to construction, agro-based, energy-based, and mineral

industries. Similarly Lalitpur comes in the second with 229 service, 208 manufacturing, 110 tourism industries and the rest 59 are related to agro-based, construction and energy-based industries [4].The figure 2.4 shows that the industries related to manufacturing, service and tourism sector are registered more in number.

Figure 2.4 Number of Industries Registered (Nov. 2014)

2.6 Average Household Waste Generation & Monthly Expenditure Level

As family size and income are the most significant factors affecting the quantity of solid waste from household consumption, a study on the relationship among these is vital in the decision making on waste management strategies. Solid waste generation depends on the economy of the people and level of income of the family or individual. It is a common observation that with an increase of economic growth the waste generation grows in an equal manner. The research shows that a high degree of positive correlation ($r = 0.96$) tends to exist between average daily waste generation (kg/household) and communities average expenditure (Rs/ household). If the monthly expenditure increases the household waste generation rate also increases.

Figure 2.5 shows that the household having average monthly expenditure of less than Rs. 5000 will generate 0.57 kg/household of average daily waste. The household whose monthly expenditure level is more than Rs. 40,000 will generate more waste i.e. average daily waste generation is 1.25 kg per household.

Figure 2.5 Average Household Waste Generations by Monthly Expenditure Level

Wealthier individuals consume more than lower-income ones, which result in a higher waste generation rate for the former. Income and household size are the most significant factors affecting the quantity of solid wastes from household consumption.

(Source: ADB, 2013)

Figure 2.6 Average Household Size and Average Household Waste in Five Municipalities

Figure 2.6 shows the average household size in Kathmandu MPC is 4.74 and average per capita household waste generation is 232.31 gm per capita per day. The average household size in Lalitpur Municipality is 4.84 and the average per capita household waste generation is 185.91 gm/capita/day. By taking the average of Bhaktapur, Thimi and Kirtipur it is found is that mean household size is 5.47 while the mean per capita household waste generation is 147.96 gm/capita/day [8]. The possible reasons for the waste generation are not only the population, urbanization,

expenditures, household size but also the modern life style of people living in the Kathmandu valley.

2.7 Characteristics of Municipality’s Waste

Often composed of very useful matter, municipality solid waste is an underutilized resource throughout the Kathmandu valley, but it also presents many unique challenges. Income levels, economic growth, and changing lifestyles affect MSW composition. In general, most of the MSW generated contains high fractions of organics and paper, compared to the lower amounts of plastics, glass, and metals. Poorer households generate higher fractions of organic waste than wealthy ones. High fractions of organics lead to a dense and humid waste that affects not only the collection and transport system, but also its recycling results in a higher percentage of inorganic materials such as metals, plastics, and glass.

Figure 2.7 Compositions of Household, Commercial & Institutional Wastes

The municipalities of Kathmandu valley have categorized municipal solid waste into different categories as organic, plastic, paper and paper products, glass, metal, textiles, rubber and leather and other wastes. Although the nature of waste varies according to the living standards and the time of year, municipal waste in the Kathmandu valley can generally be characterized as having high organic, high density and fairly high moisture content. Figure 2.7 shows different compositions of household, institutional and

commercial wastes in five municipalities of the Kathmandu valley.

Figure 2.8 Average Waste Composition in Kathmandu Valley (% by weight in 2013)

Figure 2.8 shows that the organic waste covers a high percentage of waste generated by municipalities. Of the total solid waste generated on the daily basis inside the Kathmandu valley, the composition of waste generated on the average was 42.2% organic, 25% paper and paper products, 18.8% plastic, 1.8% glass, 1.6% textiles, 1.3% metal, 0.6% rubber and leather and 8.7% other wastes. Organic waste is a biodegradable waste that can be used for composting. But all the collected organic waste cannot be converted into useful compost.

2.8 Waste Collection

As the waste generation rate is high, the municipalities of Kathmandu valley are not capable of collecting all waste generated per day. These municipalities collect waste with average efficiency of 66.42% only but remaining average 33.58% waste remains uncollected in the street and fields. The calculated value shows that Kathmandu and Bhaktapur have average of about 86.7% of waste collection efficiency, followed by Lalitpur and Thimi whereas Kirtipur has the lowest i.e. 35.3% of waste collection efficiency [9]. The reason for this is that Kathmandu and Lalitpur have landfill sites (i.e. Sisdole currently) but other municipalities dump the waste on the temporary land used for dumping the waste. Higher efficiency is also

found in Bhaktapur municipality as it has its own composting plant and the people of Bhaktapur and Thimi use waste for making bio fertilizer that can be used in their own agricultural land.

(Source: swmtsc.gov.np)

Figure 2.9 Waste Collection Efficiency of Five Municipalities

2.9 Solid Waste Management Budget

In the year 2012/13 Kathmandu MPC spent 23.32% of budget for solid waste management out of the total municipality budget of Rs. 1900 million. Bhaktapur Municipality had allocated 13.95% of budget out of the total budget of Rs.385 million. Lalitpur had Rs.558.69 million of total budgets but only 5.59% was allocated to solid waste management in the year 2012. In other municipalities fewer amounts were allocated to solid waste management compared to these municipalities [9].

(Source: swm&rmc)

Figure 2.10 Solid Waste Management Budget % of Total Municipal Budget (in Rs. Million)

Out of 2-23% of the available solid waste management budget, these municipalities spent around 90% of the budget in cleaning streets, collecting and transporting solid waste to the landfill site whereas the remaining 10% of the budget was allocated to other waste management activities.

Figure 2.11 Total Municipal Budget & solid waste Management Budget in Fiscal year 2012/13

3. DISCUSSION

From the study and data analysis it is found that there is an increasing trend of waste generation rate in the Kathmandu valley. The average per capita municipal solid waste generation is 464.61gm/capita/day in Kathmandu MPC, 371.82, 345.4, 273.44 and 252.9 gm/capita/day in Lalitpur, Bhaktapur, Thimi and Kirtipur respectively [9].

Among different types of wastes, household waste, commercial waste and institutional waste are generated highly in the Kathmandu valley. Kathmandu MPC only generates 466.14 tons of waste per day followed by Lalitpur which is 457 tons per day. Modern life style, urbanization, migration and unplanned urban development in the Kathmandu Valley have led to rapid and uncontrolled waste generation. There is a positive correlation between monthly expenditure and household waste generation in the Kathmandu valley.

Wealthier household generates more solid waste than the low income household.

The composition of municipal solid waste includes organic, paper and paper products, plastics, glass, textiles, metal, rubber and leather and other wastes. In this composition, 40% to 60% of MSW is organic in municipalities of Kathmandu valley. This organic waste is a biodegradable waste that can be used for composting which is the best solution for reducing waste on the landfill site.

Municipal solid waste collection systems consume a significant portion of the city's revenues. Collection is labour, fuel, and vehicle intensive, and needs to be repeated daily. Commonly in Kathmandu valley where people do not cooperate with waste collection systems and where traffic and road access slows the productivity of the workers and vehicles, the waste collection efficiency of municipality is not remarkable.

The solid waste management activities carried out by the government are not sufficient to reduce municipal solid waste in the Kathmandu valley. The municipalities of the valley are not capable of collecting all waste generated per day. The waste collection efficiency of these municipalities is 82% on average. Despite their effort, about 18% of waste remains uncollected and unmanaged in many places of municipalities. At present (in 2015) the Kathmandu Metropolitan City (KMC) spends 10 % of its annual budget (Rs 500 million this year) in transporting waste from its collection center at Teku to the landfill site at Sisdole (<http://swmtsc.gov.np/news-events>). The 2011 Solid Waste Management Act sets regulations and fines for transgressors and requires every household to sort waste, but enforcement has been weak largely due to unclear guidelines [9].

Instead of throwing and dumping in temporary collection centre and landfill site many benefits can be obtained by municipal solid waste with the focus on reducing the

waste and increasing the life of the landfill site.

Emerging opportunities for MSW as a strategic resource

The highest priority, avoiding and reducing the generation of waste, encourages the household, institutions and commercial sectors to reduce the amount of materials extracted and used. Focus should be given to avoid unnecessary consumption through behaviours such as selecting items with the least packaging or that require the fewest resources to produce, avoiding disposable goods or single-use materials, buying products that are recycled, recyclable, repairable, refillable, re-usable or biodegradable and using leftover food rather than throwing it away [1].

Re-use and Re-fill

Where avoiding and reducing waste is not possible, the most preferred option is to re-use the materials without further processing, avoiding the costs of energy and other resources required for recycling. For example, many household and industrial items can be repaired, re-used, sold or donated to charities. Re-using discarded goods without reprocessing or remanufacturing is assumed to provide greater savings in resource consumption and is given priority over recycling.

In the Kathmandu valley there is practice of cleaning and re-using or re-filling waste materials, for example, empty used bottles of beverages, water jar, old books, gas cylinders, undamaged jute sack and plastics sacks, etc. Plastics waste is also used to make handicrafts. Shoes sole are separated from shoes and send to shoe industries. Newspaper is also used for packaging. Some iron rods are straightened for re-use. Clear glass or plastic containers are frequently re-used in homes for other purpose.

Once a product has been used, it can either be reused or recycled. From an environmental point of view, it is much better to re-use a waste material than to recycle it. Re-using

waste often requires collection but relatively little or no processing. Less energy is used in the collecting, cleaning and re-filling of a material than is needed in recycling it. If waste materials are sent for recycling, there are also the additional costs of collecting, transporting and cleaning. It is suggested to use durable products rather than 'use and throw products'.

Composting

The organic waste generated in municipalities of Kathmandu valley is higher than other categories. Composting at the household level is an important method for managing organic waste, which is normally the largest portion of household waste i.e. 40-60% in municipalities of the Kathmandu Valley. Waste minimization and managing of waste close to the source are the two most important tools for reducing cost and improving efficiency of waste management systems. Composting reduces the environmental impacts of waste and the produced compost is essential for improving soil fertility and structure.

Production of compost at home will encourage the use of organic farming, reduce the need for chemical fertilizers, reducing the cost of solid waste management and reduce haphazard waste disposal and its related environmental impacts. Separation of organic waste and composting at the household level ensures that the remaining waste is clean and easier to recycle.

Recycling

Increased scarcity of natural resources and the consequent rise in commodity prices have influenced the demand for recycled products in the Kathmandu valley. The resource value of waste has become an important driver in municipalities today and provides a livelihood for the urban poor. Recycling is the recovery of useful materials, such as paper, glass, plastic, and metals, from the trash to use to make new products, reducing the amount of raw materials needed.

Although most of Kathmandu valley's waste can be recycled and municipality's policy is to maximize recycling, very little of Kathmandu valley's waste is actually recycled. Out of 466.14 tons per day waste generation, about 5% of waste is believed to be recycled in Kathmandu [5]. The waste materials sent for recycling from Kathmandu valley are PET plastic bottles, glass, aluminium cans, metal, textiles, newspaper, magazines, books, cardboard, CDs, batteries, disposable plates & cups, compact fluorescent bulbs (CFL), electronic equipment, etc. The recycling rate is particularly low for materials whose market value is low. This includes organic waste, some types of plastics and different coloured broken glasses. If more focus is given on recycling in the Kathmandu valley it will help to make the city clean, reduce waste, save energy, be good for economy, reduce environmental pollution, ease garbage in landfills, create new market demand for recycled materials and create job for people to manage waste, etc. [7].

Recovery

Where further recycling is not feasible, it may be possible to produce energy from the waste material and feed it back into the economy. Energy recovery from waste is the conversion of non-recyclable waste materials into useable heat, electricity, or fuel through a variety of processes, including combustion, gasification, anaerobic digestion, and landfill gas (LFG) recovery.

Municipal solid waste generated from municipalities holds immense potential for generating energy at a time when the country is undergoing a huge energy crisis. Demand for energy is increasing daily in Nepal, and the huge energy deficit has forced us to think of alternative sources of energy, and energy from waste seems to show great promise.

In rural part of the municipalities of Kathmandu Valley, there is a practice of installation of bio-gas plant which produces enough energy for household cooking. Every bio-gas plant can save 1.25 trees each year

from being copped down for fuel. Bio-gas not only replaces wood for fuel, it can also help reduce carbon emissions [1].

While MSW conversion to energy results in new emissions, the conversion of that new material into heat, gas, or liquid allows that resource to be consumed again as a feedstock for energy conversion. MSW left to decompose in landfills also produces methane gas, a Greenhouse Gas (GHG) more than twenty times more potent than carbon dioxide (CO₂).

Disposal of Waste

Land disposal is an essential part of every municipality solid waste management system. Some materials may be inappropriate to reuse, recycle or recover for energy and instead require treatment to stabilize them and minimize their environmental or health impacts.

According to Solid Waste Management and Resource Mobilization Center, 40 to 50 percent of the Valley's garbage goes to Sisdole, and most of it enters the dump unsegregated. The rest ends up on the streets and rivers. Without a mechanism to segregate waste at source, most of the organic, recyclable wastes at present end up in landfills. The only form of segregation is done by scavengers who collect plastics and other resalable materials from the site [9]. With increasing per capita waste production, the current mechanism of collecting and dumping is not going to work for long. The only functioning landfill at Sisdole is almost full, and the long-term disposal site in nearby Banchara Danda has not been completed even a decade after it was started which may bring a waste disposal problem to municipalities of the Kathmandu valley.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The municipal solid waste (MSW) opportunity is substantial across all municipalities in Nepal. A truly democratized resource, all societies generate waste, and in turn, must devise strategies for managing it. Although

population growth, urbanization, expenditure level and household size are not the only indicators of waste generation, they are critical ones. The municipalities of Kathmandu Valley accounts for around seventy percentage of the total municipal solid waste generated per day from the existing municipalities in the country. The significant rise in municipal solid wastes inside Kathmandu valley has not only contributed to environmental and social challenges such as river pollution, lack of landfill site and deplorable local environment, but has also caused huge economic loss to the government authorities due to their inability to properly manage solid wastes.

Municipal solid waste is a particularly challenging feedstock to work with due to its heterogeneity and variation in composition across municipalities. Composed of paper, plastics, organics, metal, glass, textiles and other carbon-rich material, the generation of municipal solid waste can be successfully minimized by applying measures like reduction at the source, reuse, composting, recycle and recovery of energy as it is an ideal renewable energy resource and it is generated near areas of high demand for energy. The major challenges of solid waste management in municipalities are lack of data and awareness, appropriate solid waste management technologies, and shortage of qualified human resource in policy making and implementation sector.

This study contributes towards the factors that are responsible for municipal solid waste generation in municipalities of Kathmandu valley and focusing on municipal solid waste as a strategic resource that can be reuse, compost, recycle, and recover energy which would be the better option to reduce the disposal and landfill load. This paper will be helpful for municipalities and researchers to step forward to value municipal solid waste as a strategic resource.

For Kathmandu valley, calculating the amount of waste generated and other data analysis is challenging because some of the

municipalities do not track waste generation, recycling, cost of waste management and disposal statistics properly. If municipality is capable of collecting data and maintaining statistics of the waste generated, recycled waste materials, recovered energy and also cost of recycling, disposal and waste management in different years, further detailed study can be conducted considering all the municipalities of Nepal and thereby analyzing the facts and figures of solid waste in order to move towards a sustainable future.

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